

**The impact of emissions reduction awareness on moral self-concept: Sustaining
climate-friendly behaviour in the aftermath of the COVID-19 pandemic**

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Abstract

Communication campaigns often highlight environmental progress to encourage further pro-environmental behaviour. Consequently, the drop in carbon emissions caused by the COVID-19 restrictions has been framed as a positive environmental outcome of the pandemic. We conducted an experimental study with a US representative sample (N = 500) to show that raising awareness of emissions reduction has the contrary effect: An increase in moral self-concept facilitated a negative spillover, namely, it reduced climate-friendly behavioural intentions. Normative influence was able to prevent this negative spillover because activating environmental norms inhibited compensatory feelings. Besides, awareness of recent emissions reduction was less likely to increase the moral self-concept of participants with a strong environmental self-identity. Our findings demonstrate that environmental progress increases moral self-concept which, in turn, could cause a negative spillover (i.e., reduce climate-friendly low-carbon behaviour and increase climate-harmful high-carbon behaviour). Normative influences and environmental self-identity can inhibit this negative spillover.

Keywords: behavioural spillover, low-carbon behaviour, COVID-19, norms, environmental self-identity

1. INTRODUCTION

Research on the impact of COVID-19 on climate action has shown that disruptive changes in daily life have led individuals to adopt pro-environmental behaviours, such as reducing food waste (Jribi et al. 2020) or consuming less energy (Ghiani et al. 2020). Overall, COVID-19 circumstances caused a temporary drop in carbon (CO₂) emissions (Le Quéré et al. 2020), which constitutes a communication opportunity; by framing recent environmental progress (i.e. emissions reduction) as an outcome of individuals' behaviour change (Dandy 2020), campaigners can try to motivate further pro-environmental behaviour (Gifford and Comeau 2011, Spence and Pidgeon 2010). This phenomenon, in which an initial pro-environmental act leads to subsequent pro-environmental actions, is known as *positive spillover* or *consistency behaviour* (Hartmann et al. 2017, Thøgersen 1999, Lauren et al. 2019).

However, environmental campaigns may not be as effective as previously thought in generating positive spillovers and may even trigger adverse effects by making people less concerned and less motivated to behave pro-environmentally (Hornsey and Fielding 2016, Hart and Nisbet 2012). This is particularly worrying given that messages highlighting the CO₂ emissions reduction may signal that individuals have contributed sufficiently to the environment, making them feel entitled to give up future pro-environmental behaviours. Indeed, a COVID-19-induced emissions-reduction message may backfire if it causes a *compensatory behaviour or moral licensing*, that is, a negative spillover in which a prior action provides a "license" allowing one to exhibit morally questionable behaviour later on (Monin and Miller 2001, Merritt, Effron, and Monin 2010).

Inadvertently, news celebrating a great reduction in CO₂ emissions during the COVID-19 pandemic may facilitate a negative spillover in the aftermath of the

pandemic. To date, researchers have been unable to provide an overarching model that predicts positive and negative behavioural spillovers (Truelove et al. 2014), but a closer examination of moral values seems to be a promising departing framework (Vincent and Koessler 2020). Thus, a deeper understanding of the behavioural mechanisms underpinning negative spillovers is needed to clarify competing theoretical explanations and mixed empirical results (Carrico 2021). Previous studies have already argued that environmental cues may create a negative spillover (Margetts and Kashima 2017), but negative spillovers have not yet been studied as such in the context of global emissions reduction.

The present research addresses these gaps in the literature by integrating insights from COVID-19–related moral decision-making (Bouman, Steg, and Dietz 2021) and behavioural spillover literature (Truelove et al. 2014, Gholamzadehmir, Sparks, and Farsides 2019, Vincent and Koessler 2020, Carrico 2021) to devise a model to explain the driving forces of negative spillovers in the environmental domain in the aftermath of the pandemic. Specifically, we studied whether and under what conditions negative spillovers occurred when participants were aware of emissions reduction, as well as repercussions on intentions to engage in climate-friendly (low-carbon) and climate-harmful (high-carbon) behaviour. We conducted two experimental studies, a pilot study with graduate university students and a main study with a US-representative sample, to examine whether providing information to raise awareness of COVID-19-induced carbon emissions reductions triggered negative spillovers, curtailing climate action, and whether this process can be mitigated. Following Khan and Dhar’s (2006) experiments on moral licensing, we examined the effects on the malleable part of the relevant self-concept that changes relative to the traits of a prototypically moral person (i.e. the moral self-concept).

The contribution of this research is threefold. First, rising awareness of COVID-19-induced emissions reduction enhances moral self-concept in the environmental domain. Second, awareness of emissions reduction reduces climate-friendly low-carbon behaviour and facilitates climate-harmful behaviours through a negative spillover. Third, normative influence and self-reported environmental self-identity (i.e., the extent to which individuals see themselves as someone who acts in an environmentally friendly way (Van der Werff, Steg, and Keizer 2013)) are identified as exogenous and endogenous factors, respectively, capable of preventing a negative spillover. We manipulated norms' salience during the survey to remind participants of the common consensus on the need for action to address climate change.

The experiment presented in this research uses information provision about the unintended environmental consequences of a collective and mandatory action (i.e. halting normal life due to COVID-19) to trigger a negative behavioural spillover at personal level. In this case, the difficulty of generating a negative spillover resides in the abstract construal of information (Mullen and Monin 2016), because the manipulation only asked participants to remember the result of a collective public health action, which does not belong to the same domain as the behavioural intentions the experiment tried to influence (i.e. individual low-carbon behaviour and climate-harmful behaviour). Hence, detecting a negative behavioural spillover at this level of abstraction would imply that providing impersonal or general information about environmental progress is enough to trigger negative behavioural spillovers in the environmental domain.

The next section integrates behavioural spillover, normative influence, and environmental self-identity concepts within a theoretical framework to develop the model and hypotheses on the behavioural outcomes of awareness of carbon emissions reduction. Thereafter, we present the results of the test of the proposed model.

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

2.1. Compensatory effects of Covid-19-induced emissions reduction

Behavioral changes in general, and spillovers in particular, can either contribute to climate change mitigation by amplifying pro-environmental behaviour, or hinder climate action by facilitating future behaviours that undermine the net effects of environmental progress (Carrico 2021). Being crucial to address climate change, the decision to engage or not engage in pro-environmental behaviours is often subject to moralisation (Butler 2010). Although giving up low-carbon behaviours or adopting climate-harmful behaviours could be regarded as morally questionable, individuals can derive confidence to perform these actions by reflecting on their past moral behaviour (Merritt, Efron, and Monin 2010). Moral licensing occurs when past behaviour makes individuals more likely to act immorally without worrying about feeling or appearing immoral (Monin and Miller 2001) because their previous behaviour secures their moral image (Miller and Efron 2010).

The negative spillover attributed to moral licensing in the environmental domain is driven by individuals' feelings of entitlement to act in a way they would not permit themselves without having performed a pro-environmental action first (Gholamzadehmir, Sparks, and Farsides 2019). This phenomenon has been widely reported (Blanken, van de Ven, and Zeelenberg 2015); for instance, researchers found that engaging in sustainable energy behaviours in the past decreased support for subsequent climate-friendly policies (Noblet and McCoy 2018). Also, people were less generous after purchasing a sustainable product (Mazar and Zhong 2010), or reduced pro-environmental behaviour after donating to a charity organization (Meijers et al. 2015).

Nonetheless, operationalising compensatory intentions in the environmental domain has proven to be difficult (Carrico et al. 2018). Khan and Dhar (2006) conceptualised moral licensing feelings as an increase in *moral self-concept*, showing that an enhancement of moral self-concept was an antecedent of a future negative spillover. In several subsequent studies, changes in moral self-concept have also been conceptualised as antecedents of moral licensing (Mazar and Zhong 2010, Merritt, Effron, and Monin 2010, Sachdeva, Iliev, and Medin 2009). This kind of negative spillover is thus preceded by an increase in moral self-concept, triggered by a prior pro-environmental contribution (Khan and Dhar 2006).

Awareness of COVID-19-induced carbon emissions reduction may serve as a justification that frees participants from the moral obligation of performing further environmental behaviours in the future, making participants feel entitled to reduce their low-carbon behavioural intentions and increase their carbon footprint. Since evidence shows that cognitive accessibility and awareness of a previous good deed are necessary to enable a negative spillover (Miller and Effron 2010, Sintov, Geislar, and White 2019), we hypothesise that raising awareness of the environmental progress caused by COVID-19 will enhance the participants' moral self-concept regarding their carbon emissions.

H1: Awareness of carbon emissions reduction caused by the COVID-19 pandemic increases moral self-concept.

Enhancing moral self-concept can reduce the motivation to engage in subsequent pro-environmental behaviour because individuals feel they no longer need to establish their morality. Regarding negative spillovers generated by past pro-environmental actions, Gholamzadehmir, Sparks, and Farsides (2019) showed that reminding people of previous pro-environmental behaviour made them less likely to seek information about

their carbon footprint. Merritt, Effron, and Monin (2010) concluded that an increase in moral self-concept is the first step towards a negative spillover, making one feel entitled to perform a morally dubious act next.

Individuals whose awareness of COVID-19-induced emissions reduction has been risen may feel moral with regard to their emissions reduction. Hence, we hypothesise that the future negative spillover belongs to the environmental domain and will likely be an emissions-related behaviour, that is, a climate-friendly or climate-harmful behaviour. Consequently, the negative spillover process begins with emissions reduction awareness enhancing moral self-concept, which in turn weakens the drive to engage in low-carbon behaviour and increases the likelihood of performing climate-harmful behaviours.

H2: Awareness of carbon emissions reduction caused by the COVID-19 pandemic decreases low-carbon behaviour via an increase in moral self-concept.

2.2. Inhibiting influences of norm activation

When receiving information about a recent achievement, individuals can interpret their past actions in two ways. In a *commitment representation*, the new information would reinforce individuals' dedication towards pursuing the same goal, while a *progress representation* would allow them to balance between keep contributing to the goal and overlook it to pursue others (Fishbach, Zhang, and Koo 2009). Since framing information as progress towards a goal has been shown to facilitate a negative behavioral spillover (Fishbach and Dhar 2005), presenting emissions reduction as progress towards a climate goal may induce people to feel liberated from the obligation of making any additional contribution (e.g. adopting low-carbon behaviour). Conversely, when past actions signal adherence to the goal, individuals are prompted

towards a commitment interpretation that reduces the likelihood of negative spillovers (Fishbach, Zhang, and Koo 2009).

Given that individuals' moral interpretation of their past actions can be manipulated (Cornelissen et al. 2013), designing messages that shift attention from progress to commitment may contribute to preventing negative spillovers in future actions. Making norms salient can facilitate a commitment representation because social norms are rules for behaviour to which members of a group commit (Turner 1991). Indeed, appealing to environmental norms has proven to be an effective strategy to encourage pro-environmental behaviours, such as recycling and waste prevention (Cialdini, Reno, and Kallgren 1990); reducing energy use (Allcott 2011); and promoting more sustainable means of transportation (Kormos, Gifford, and Brown 2015).

Despite norm manipulation having been extensively used to encourage pro-environmental behaviour, scarce evidence exists on the specific effect of normative influences on negative spillovers (Dorner 2019, Fanghella, D'Adda, and Tavoni 2019). Bissing-Olson, Fielding, and Iyer (2016) asked university students to report their engagement in specific pro-environmental behaviours during the day and whether they felt proud or guilty for performing such actions. Participants who performed pro-environmental behaviours reported higher levels of self-image. However, from the student group feeling upright about their past pro-environmental behaviours, only those who perceived positive pro-environmental descriptive norms engaged in subsequent environmentally friendly behaviours. Similarly, we expect a much weaker negative spillover in participants aware of environmental norms. The focus theory of normative conduct (Cialdini, Reno, and Kallgren 1990) stipulates that making norms salient is key to focusing attention on the recommended behaviour and motivating individuals to comply. Nolan et al. (2008) showed that pro-environmental behaviour was more

effectively encouraged with normative information about conservation behaviour than with information about potential environmental impacts. Similar studies about water conservation (Schultz et al. 2016) and energy use (Schultz et al. 2007) have found that making environmental norms salient was more influential than past actions themselves to enhance subsequent pro-environmental behaviours. Manipulating normative influence should affect behavioural responses to COVID-19-induced emissions-reduction awareness because norms shift attention from concrete environmental progress to environmental commitment (Cornelissen et al. 2013, Bouman, Steg, and Dietz 2021). Therefore, we hypothesise that the activation of negative spillovers caused by information provision aimed at raising awareness of COVID-19-induced emissions reduction will be inhibited by making environmental norms salient.

H3a: Norm activation inhibits the increase in moral self-concept generated by the awareness of carbon emissions reduction caused by the COVID-19 pandemic.

H3b: Norm activation inhibits the negative effect of awareness of carbon emissions reduction caused by the COVID-19 pandemic on low-carbon behaviour through moral self-concept.

2.3. Inoculating effects of environmental self-identity

Self-identity is the salient part of self-concept that relates to a particular behaviour (Conner and Armitage 1998). Van der Werff, Steg, and Keizer (2013) define environmental self-identity as the extent to which an individual sees oneself as a person whose actions are environmentally friendly. Specifically, biospheric values determine environmental self-identity because they reflect what individuals find important and how they want to see themselves (Van der Werff, Steg, and Keizer 2013). Individuals with a high environmental self-identity are more likely to act in line with this identity in the future. Therefore, individuals' identification with future behaviour (i.e. Being able

to establish a connection between one's behaviour and one's values and identity) should determine the direction of the behavioural spillover (Mullen and Monin 2016).

Environmental self-identity has been proposed to mediate both positive and negative spillovers (Geng et al. 2019). Although scholars agree that a strong environmental self-identity contributes to positive spillovers in pro-environmental behaviour (Meijers 2014, Poortinga, Whitmarsh, and Suffolk 2013), the same consensus does not exist on the role a weak environmental self-identity plays in facilitating negative spillovers. After only obtaining marginally significant results, studies investigating the role of environmental self-identity as a mediator (Truelove et al. 2016) or as a manipulation (Fanghella, D'Adda, and Tavoni 2019, Maki et al. 2019) have concluded that environmental self-identity alone is not a reliable factor to determine the direction of behavioural spillovers.

Even if environmental self-identity can be influenced by past behaviour, the biospheric values that determine environmental self-identity are only somewhat malleable (Van der Werff, Steg, and Keizer 2014). Given that the uncertain and variable nature of negative spillovers (Blanken, van de Ven, and Zeelenberg 2015) contrasts with the rather stable core of environmental self-identity, some authors (Carfora et al. 2017, Meijers et al. 2019) propose a moderating role of environmental self-identity in negative spillover processes rather than a mediating effect. For instance, Meijers et al. (2019) found that environmental self-identity remained relatively stable after the participants purchased a green product (no mediating effect), yet self-identity moderated the influence of that initial action on subsequent pro-environmental behaviour.

Overall, when subsequent behaviour is a direct test of individuals' values and noncompliance may put their environmentalist identity at risk, low identifiers engage in negative spillovers (Mullen and Monin 2016), whereas high identifiers keep behaviour

consistent to maintain their self-concept (Mazar and Zhong 2010, Meijers et al. 2019) and avoid cognitive dissonance (Bem 1972). Therefore, we expect a moderating effect, making participants with a strong environmental self-identity less likely to engage in the negative spillover caused by emissions reduction awareness.

H4a: Environmental self-identity inhibits the increase in moral self-concept generated by the awareness of carbon emissions reductions caused by the COVID-19 pandemic.

H4b: Environmental self-identity inhibits the negative effect of awareness of carbon emissions reductions caused by the COVID-19 pandemic on low-carbon behaviour through moral self-concept.

Figure 1 illustrates the hypothesised negative spillover of raising emissions reduction awareness on low-carbon behaviour.

3. METHOD

3.1. Validating the feasibility of the experiment

Before conducting the main study presented below, we ran a pilot study on a smaller scale (N = 148) to assess whether emissions reduction awareness manipulation was effective and to evaluate the adequacy of the measurement items and the posterior analysis. Appendix A contains all the methodological details and results of the pilot study that informed the experimental design of the main study.

3.2. Participants and procedure

The main study was conducted as an online experiment using Qualtrics. The sample was drawn from a Prolific online panel of the US population (N = 500, 49.08% female, $M_{\text{age}} = 45.09$, $SD_{\text{age}} = 14.90$). Nine participants with incomplete and inconsistent responses were substituted by the panel provider. The sample size was

adequate because, according to MacKinnon, Fairchild, and Fritz (2007), for power = .80 and $\alpha = 0.05$, the required sample size to detect mediated effects above 0.14 (i.e., even small effects) is at least 462 participants. The subjects were selected by a quota-based random criterion to be representative of the US population in terms of age, sex, income, education, and profession, and they received monetary compensation for participating in the study (see Table B1 in Appendix B for sample characteristics).

Participants were randomly assigned to one of four experimental factor treatments of a 2 (high vs. low awareness of COVID-19-induced emissions reduction) \times 2 (norm activation vs. control) between-subjects factorial design. The awareness manipulation for COVID-19-induced emissions reduction was the same as in the pilot study and in the pretest manipulation check. After exposure to the experimental stimuli, participants responded to an online questionnaire, rating items on moral self-concept, environmental self-identity, and the likelihood of their performing a set of low-carbon and climate-harmful behaviours. After the main questionnaire, the norm manipulation was assessed, and participants responded to demographic questions.

3.3. Emissions reduction awareness and environmental norms manipulations

Participants in both the high- and the low-awareness groups were exposed to a text asking them to reflect on their personal impact on carbon emissions (*“Please think about the carbon footprint of your lifestyle, that is, the amount of carbon emissions released into the atmosphere as a result of your consumption habits and decisions”*). In the high-awareness group, the text included an additional paragraph informing them of the reduction of carbon emissions as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic: *“According to the international research initiative Carbon Monitor, our collective effort to stay at home during the COVID-19 pandemic has had a beneficial effect on our climate too. As a consequence of the lockdown, restrictions, and decrease in travel, daily carbon*

emissions (CO₂) decreased by 14% in the United States (338 million metric tons less of CO₂ in 2020). Your sacrifice by changing your lifestyle to save lives has also reduced your carbon emissions considerably during the last months.” The emissions reduction data were retrieved from the latest reports available at the time of the study (Le Quéré et al. 2020). Importantly, we considered environmental self-identity a moderator rather than a mediator of our model, and the experimental design ensured that the salience of environmental self-identity was not unintentionally manipulated along with the awareness manipulation (see Appendix A) because that could have affected the direction of the spillover (e.g. Geng et al. 2019).

The environmental norms manipulation used to exert normative influence was similar to manipulations used in past research (Larimer and Neighbors 2003, Smith et al. 2008). For participants in the norm activation condition an additional paragraph was inserted before the text on environmental behaviour and the emission awareness manipulation: *“In a recent representative survey of the US population, more than 65% of the participants were very concerned about climate change and agreed with the statement that we should take urgent action against global warming by reducing our carbon emissions. People that are close and important to you may expect you to reduce your carbon emissions too.”*

Manipulation check results were significant for both awareness manipulation ($t(1, 98) = -2.83, p = .006$) and norms’ manipulation ($t(1,498) = -2.69, p = .007$), confirming their potential to influence participants’ perceptions. The results of these statistical tests are reported in more detail in Appendix A.

3.4. Measurement

After the corresponding manipulation information was administered to the treatment groups, participants answered an online questionnaire. To measure *low-*

carbon behavioural intention, they were asked to rate on a five-point Likert-type scale (1 = *very unlikely* to 5 = *very likely*) how likely they were in the following two months to perform the seven low-carbon behaviours previously tested in the pilot study, which were adapted from the pro-environmental behaviour index (Kaiser and Wilson 2004). Additionally, we negatively worded seven low-carbon behaviours (Bissing-Olson, Fielding, and Iyer 2016) to build a climate-harmful behavioural-intention scale. The aim of collecting data on both low-carbon and climate-harmful intentions was to show that awareness of emissions reduction not only lowers intention to engage in low-carbon behaviour but also gives rise to intentions to engage in climate-harmful behaviour.

To assess *moral self-concept*, participants were first requested to “*reflect about your impact on carbon emissions and climate change, both about the things you do that are harmful to the climate and the actions that help fight global warming.*” Then, we asked them to rate how they felt about their carbon emissions on four five-point semantic differential scales (e.g., *guilty-virtuous*). Other than the single item used in the pilot study, the items were based on the moral self-concept scales more commonly used in previous research (Carrico et al. 2018, Khan and Dhar 2006, Cornelissen et al. 2013).

The remaining variables were rated on five-point Likert-type scales (1 = *strongly disagree* to 5 = *strongly agree*). *Environmental self-identity* was measured using a three-item scale by Van der Werff, Steg, and Keizer (2013). Because the negative spillovers effects of information provision about emissions reduction may vary depending on each participant’s unique experience during the COVID-19 pandemic, we controlled for the degree to which participants actually performed the initial behaviour they are informed about in the manipulation. Therefore, we adapted the items used by Carrico et al. (2018) to measure the *behavioural difficulty to comply with COVID-19 measures* as a covariate

in our analyses to consider the costliness of the behaviour that led to the emissions reduction. All measurement scales and their properties are displayed in Table 1.

3.5. Statistical analysis

For testing H1, we used an independent samples t-test to compare the mean moral self-concept reported by participants in the high awareness and low awareness groups and determine whether there was a statistically significant difference between them.

Next, we tested the mediation proposed in H2 with a regression analysis. This mediation refers to the hypothesized causal chain in which raising awareness of emissions reduction affects moral self-concept (the mediator) which, in turn, affects behavioural intentions. We computed this indirect regression using PROCESS' SPSS macro for mediated regression analysis (Hayes, 2017). Specifically, we used PROCESS' Model 4 because it analyses a simple mediation path without moderators. The indirect regression coefficient of Model 4 reflected the effect the awareness manipulation had in low-carbon and climate-harmful behaviours, mediated by moral self-concept.

The following steps of the analysis addressed the moderating influence of norms and environmental self-identity on the awareness–self-concept link, assessing whether the effect of the awareness manipulation on moral self-concept varied depending on norms activation (H3a) or on the level of environmental self-identity (H4a). Hayes (2017) recommends looking for a significant moderation on the effect of the independent variable (the awareness manipulation) on the mediator (moral self-concept), as it is generally a prerequisite for the moderation of a mediated influence. We used PROCESS' Model 7, which extends Model 4 by including a moderator in the first part of the mediation, to individually test whether the interaction coefficients (norms and environmental self-identity) were significant in a regression with moral self-concept as the dependent variable.

Lastly, using PROCESS' Model 9 we tested whether norms and environmental self-identity complemented each other in the same mediation and influenced not only moral self-concept, but also behavioural intentions. PROCESS computes an index of moderated mediation and bootstrap confidence intervals to test the significance of the moderation of indirect effects. Subsequently, in the result section, we examined the lower and upper limit bootstrap confidence intervals (Boot LLCI, Boot ULCI): When the bootstrap confidence interval does not contain zero, the significance of the moderated mediation index is confirmed. This conditional effects analysis disentangled the variation in the indirect effect of the awareness manipulation via moral self-concept when norms were absent or activated (H3b), and also at three different levels of environmental self-identity (H4b): at one standard deviation below the mean value of the moderator (-1 SD), at the mean value of the moderator (M), and one standard deviation above the mean value of the moderator (+1 SD).

4. RESULTS

4.1. Mediation analysis

Participants in the COVID-19 emissions reduction awareness manipulation reported higher levels of moral self-concept ($M = 3.10$, $SD = 0.85$) than the control group ($M = 2.87$, $SD = 0.90$, $t(1,498) = -2.89$, $p = .004$, Cohen's $d = -0.26$), confirming H1. Table 2 shows the mean group differences for the variables moral self-concept, low-carbon behaviour and climate-harmful behaviour.

A mediation analysis with 10,000 bootstrap samples (PROCESS, Model 4; Hayes 2017) confirmed there was a negative effect of emissions reduction awareness on future low-carbon behaviours mediated by moral self-concept ($b_{ind} = -.05$, $SE = .02$, 95% bootstrap CI $[-.09, -.02]$, $ab_{ps} = -.07$), supporting H2. The mediation was complete, with

the remaining direct effect being nonsignificant ($b = .02$, $SE = .07$, $t = 0.23$, $p = .82$, 95% CI $[-.12, .15]$), implying that the relationship between emissions reduction awareness and future low-carbon behaviour was explained entirely through the boost in moral self-concept. The effect size of the simple mediation model, computed as the partially standardized indirect effect (ab_{ps}), indicated that being in the high awareness group resulted in a decrease of 0.07 standard deviations in low-carbon behaviour through its effect on self-concept. Similarly, moral self-concept mediated the positive effect of the COVID-19-induced emissions reduction message on future climate-harmful behaviour ($b_{ind} = .02$, $SE = .01$, 95% bootstrap CI $[-.01, .05]$, $ab_{ps} = .03$). This overall indirect effect being relatively weak is partly a consequence of the norm manipulation and the inoculating effect of the individual's environmental self-identity.

4.2. Moderation analysis

Moderated regression analysis using PROCESS' Model 7 confirmed a significant negative interaction of the effect of the emissions reduction awareness manipulation with the normative influence manipulation on moral self-concept ($b_{awareness \times norms} = -.47$, $SE = .15$, $t = -3.02$, $p = .003$, 95% CI $[-.77, -.16]$, $f^2 = 0.02$) and a significant negative interaction of the effect of the awareness manipulation with environmental self-identity on moral self-concept ($b_{awareness \times env. self} = -.20$, $SE = .08$, $t = -2.34$, $p = .019$, 95% CI $[-.37, -.03]$, $f^2 = 0.01$), providing support for H3a and H4a, respectively. From participants who were aware of COVID-19-induced emissions reduction, only those who did not receive environmental norms information reported a significantly higher self-concept (Figure 2). Participants with the lowest environmental self-identity in the high-awareness group reported a higher self-concept, while the moral self-concept of strong environmentalists who received the emissions reduction information did not change significantly (Figure 3). As Table 3 shows, norms

manipulation reduced moral self-concept significantly, with environmental self-identity reducing self-concept as environmentalist identification increased (for a visualization of the interaction effect of both moderators, see Figure B2 in Appendix B).

4.3. Moderated mediation analysis

Moderated mediation analysis using PROCESS' Model 9 confirmed significant moderated mediation indexes (10,000 bootstraps, 95% CI) for environmental self-identity and environmental norms, supporting H3b and H4b. Both moderated mediation indexes were significant for low-carbon and climate-harmful behavioural intentions, although the conditional effect on the latter was weaker than on the former (Table 4).

A conditional indirect effect analysis showed that the indirect effect of the emissions-awareness manipulation on low-carbon behavioural intentions mediated by moral self-concept was negative and significant in the control group ($b_{ind} = -.10$, $SE = .03$, 95% Boot CI [-.17, -.05]) but not significant and close to zero in the environmental norms group ($b_{ind} = .003$, $SE = .03$, 95% Boot CI [-.04, .05]), providing support for H3b by demonstrating that normative influence inhibits negative spillovers. Apart from the moderating effect of norm activation on low-carbon behaviour, the indirect effect was also stronger at one standard deviation below the environmental self-identity mean value (-1SD = 2.70, $b = -.14$, $SE = .04$, 95% CI [-.21, -.07]) than at the mean ($M = 3.62$, $b = -.10$, $SE = .03$, 95% CI [-.17, -.05]) and again weaker at one standard deviation above the mean (+1SD = 4.54, $b = -.07$, $SE = .04$, 95% CI [-.14, -.01]), further confirming the moderating role of environmental self-identity (H4b). Regarding the coefficient of determination (R^2), the complete model with low-carbon behaviour as the dependent variable explained 7% of the variance.

The conditional indirect effects followed the same pattern for climate-harmful behavioural intentions but with an opposite sign and a smaller explanatory power ($R^2 =$

2%). The indirect effect of the awareness manipulation on climate-harmful behaviour mediated by moral self-concept was positive and significant in the control group ($b_{\text{ind}} = .05$, $SE = .06$, 95% Boot CI [.01, .09]) but turned non-significant and close to zero when norms were activated ($b_{\text{ind}} = -.001$, $SE = .01$, 95% Boot CI [-.03, .02]). The indirect effect of the awareness manipulation was also stronger at one standard deviation below the environmental self-identity mean value (-1SD = 2.70, $b = .06$, $SE = .03$, 95% CI [.01, .12]) than at the mean ($M = 3.62$, $b = .05$, $SE = .02$, 95% CI [.01, .10]) and again weaker at one standard deviation above the mean (+1SD = 4.54, $b = .03$, $SE = .02$, 95% CI [-.001, .08]).

As a robustness check, we introduced the behavioural difficulty experienced during COVID-19 lockdowns as a covariate into the model. Introducing the covariate only marginally affected the results and did not affect the significance of the observed effects. This implies that even accounting for the efforts individuals made to adapt to COVID-19, the effects of emissions-reduction awareness and the moderating roles of environmental norms and environmental self-identity on the indirect effect remained unaltered.

4.4. Subgroup analysis of moderators' effect

The strongest conditional effect on moral self-concept occurred when environmental self-identity was low and norms were absent ($b = .59$, $SE = .13$, $t = 4.55$, $p < .001$, 95% CI [.33, .84]), suggesting that the presence of both norms and environmental identity contributed to containing moral self-concept. Yet, the moderated mediation analysis revealed that one moderator was more influential than the other.

Notably, normative influence was the overriding moderator in our complete model, because when environmental norms were activated, the effect of emissions-reduction awareness on low-carbon intentions via moral self-concept turned not

significant, regardless of the level of participant's environmental self-identity. The additional pattern we discern from the conditional analysis is that increasing levels of environmental self-identity decreases the moral self-concept effects of emissions-reduction awareness on low-carbon intentions. Climate-harmful behavioural intentions follow the same pattern, too, but in the opposite direction; namely, a strong environmental self-identity attenuates the increase in climate-harmful behaviours caused by emissions-reduction awareness. However, participants not cued with environmental norms, even those with a strong environmental self-identity, tended toward a negative spillover unless environmental norms were activated (see Figure B3 and Figure B4 in Appendix B). The results in Table 4 further show that conditional indirect effects were stronger for low-carbon than for climate-harmful behavioural intentions. This illustrates that the negative spillover caused by the awareness of COVID-19-induced emissions reduction is more salient as a reduction of low-carbon intentions than as an increase of climate-harmful intentions.

5. DISCUSSION

5.1. Contribution and theoretical implications

Our results show that providing information to raise awareness of carbon emissions reduction caused by the COVID-19 pandemic increases moral self-concept, facilitating a negative spillover that decreases the intention to engage in low-carbon behaviours and even increases the disposition to perform climate-harmful behaviours.

The effect of emission reduction awareness on future pro-environmental behaviour via moral self-concept was moderated by normative influence and environmental self-identity. The environmental norms manipulation inhibited negative spillovers by significantly curtailing the increase in moral self-concept. High levels of

environmental self-identity also reduced the boost in moral self-concept, but this moderating effect alone was not enough to entirely prevent a negative spillover: Environmental self-identity had to be combined with normative influence to be able to significantly reduce the impact of emissions reduction awareness on moral self-concept and subsequent behavioural intentions. These results are consistent across two dependent variables: A negative spillover was found when future actions were low-carbon behaviours and, to a lesser extent, when subsequent actions were a set of climate-harmful behaviours. Because performing a climate-harmful behaviour is a blatant transgression compared to the ambiguity of giving up climate-friendly, low-carbon behaviour (Brown et al. 2011), negative spillovers should indeed be more likely for the latter than for the former.

Our findings make several contributions to the growing body of research on behavioural spillovers in the moral-environmental domain (Vincent and Koessler 2020, Truelove et al. 2014), which is divided between studies backing positive spillovers (Geng et al. 2019, Margetts and Kashima 2017, Lanzini and Thøgersen 2014) and research pointing to negative spillovers (Truelove et al. 2016, Gholamzadehmir, Sparks, and Farsides 2019, Mazar and Zhong 2010). Our results are not aimed at favouring one strand of research over the other but acknowledge that even awareness of a positive initial behaviour can trigger negative spillovers unless some external or internal factors are present to inhibit them. Our research has contributed to the identification of two factors, namely normative influence and environmental self-identity, which can be leveraged to reduce the likelihood of negative behavioural spillovers.

First, our study showed that informing participants about the environmental outcome of their behaviour during lockdown increased the likelihood of negative spillovers. The prevalence of negative spillovers may be attributed to the perceived

costliness of the initial behaviour (e.g., lockdowns and restrictions). When the initial act is costless or unrelated to future behaviour, the action is not enough to signal the environmental values of the individual, and this lack of value reflection may prevent them from engaging in positive spillovers (Mullen and Monin 2016). However, in our study, negative spillovers did not change even when we introduced behavioural difficulty as a covariate in our model. This robustness check discarded the costliness of past behaviour as a relevant determinant of negative spillovers, in contrast to previous studies (Carrico et al. 2018, Truelove et al. 2016). Despite an abstract construal (i.e. not a tangible or accessible perception of the initial behaviour) making negative spillovers less likely (Mullen and Monin 2016), we demonstrated that information provision asking participants to remember the unintended environmental consequences of a collective action was enough to generate a significant negative behavioural spillover. Moreover, the negative spillover was detected even though the initial behaviour (staying at home during lockdown) did not belong to the same action domain as low-carbon behaviour and climate-harmful consumption. The negative spillover still occurred probably because individuals are able to cognitively categorize actions from different domains within a single moral rubric (Jordan, Mullen, and Murnighan 2011).

Second, making environmental norms salient has proven to be an effective strategy to prevent the negative spillovers effect caused by the awareness of COVID-19-induced emissions reduction because acting pro-environmentally constitutes a prosocial behaviour and, as such, is significantly determined by normative influence (Nolan et al. 2008, Cialdini and Goldstein 2004). That future pro-environmental behaviour can be preserved by exerting normative influence adds to the research investigating social norms to promote positive spillovers in the environmental domain (Bissing-Olson, Fielding, and Iyer 2016). The moderating role of normative influence further expands

the research strand initiated by Cornelissen et al. (2013) in which shifting participants' attention from an outcome-focused mindset (i.e. progress representation) to a rule-focused mindset (i.e. commitment representation) deactivates compensatory intentions after an ethical behaviour. As illustrated in Figure 2, the strong moderating influence of social norms was able to reduce the high awareness group's moral self-concept down to the mean moral self-concept of the low awareness group, and thus eliminate the possibility of behavioural spillovers caused by raising awareness of emissions reduction.

Third, awareness of COVID-19-induced carbon emissions reduction is less likely to generate negative spillovers when participants have a strong environmental self-identity. Figure 3 shows that, for the moral self-concept levels in the high awareness group to equal those in the low awareness group, participants needed to have a strong environmental self-identity. The weaker the environmental self-identity in the high awareness group, the higher was participants' reported moral self-concept. These results are consistent with previous studies connecting environmental self-identity to positive spillovers, in general (Geng et al. 2019, Poortinga, Whitmarsh, and Suffolk 2013), and pointing to this variable as a negative spillover moderator in particular (Meijers 2014, Meijers et al. 2019). However, our results suggest that a strong environmental self-identity is not enough to completely prevent a negative spillover. As demonstrated by Howell and Allen (2017), biospheric values alone are not enough to guarantee pro-environmental behaviour. Introducing environmental norms is necessary to inhibit negative spillovers, regardless of the individual's level of environmental self-identity. Only within the group exposed to the norms manipulation, the participants with a stronger self-identity were less likely to tend toward a negative spillover than those

with a weak identity, which suggests that awareness of normative influence is a prerequisite for the inoculating effect of environmental self-identity.

5.2. Practical implications

Highlighting COVID-19-induced emissions reduction can negatively affect pro-environmental intentions because people are prompted to worry less about climate change, as warned by Bouman et al. (2020). The implications of the present study are relevant beyond the specific case of emissions reduction caused by COVID-19 circumstances. News on environmental progress because of other reasons have produced negative results in the past as well (Hornsey and Fielding 2016).

The manipulation we used to raise awareness caused a significant negative spillover, but its effect size was small, in line with most behavioural spillover studies in the environmental domain (Maki et al. 2019). Although a single message is unlikely to shift behaviours, if individuals are frequently exposed to messages that highlight environmental progress, their perception of having contributed enough to the environment will be reinforced, and the overall impact of all these messages on low-carbon and climate-harmful behaviour will be greater over time. Our results indicate that communication campaigns unintentionally inducing negative spillovers may be more common than previously thought. Environmental campaigners and organizations aiming to communicate environmental progress in the aftermath of the pandemic can learn from these experiences to design environmental messages that do not generate compensatory feelings.

Including normative appeals can reduce negative spillovers because these promote a commitment representation by highlighting the morality of future behaviour, and nudge individuals to follow social norms (Mullen and Monin 2016). Overall, designing post-COVID-19 environmental campaigns that increase environmental self-

identity but also exert normative influence may be an effective way to convey future climate wins without triggering negative spillovers.

5.3. Limitations and directions for future research

The findings of behavioural spillover studies asking participants to remember (instead of engaging in) a behaviour should be taken with caution because the spillover effects could be different (Carrico 2021). Despite the high awareness manipulation significantly increased participants' moral self-concept, the differences regarding low-carbon and climate-harmful behavioural intentions were small and non-significant between experimental groups. The complete moderated mediation models predicting low-carbon and climate-harmful behaviour had small effect sizes (Cohen 1988). Even though both complete models were significant and the awareness manipulation was shown to significantly affect behavioural intentions via its effect on moral self-concept, a direct effect without covariates could not be proven between the awareness manipulation and behavioural intentions. The small effect size and the absence of a clear direct effect can be attributed to three major factors, but chiefly to the strong moderating influences of norms and environmental self-identity. Apart from the moderating influences that created differences within experimental groups, asking all participants to reflect on their carbon footprint might have decreased differences between groups, as participants' attention in the low awareness condition was also shifted towards low-carbon behaviour. Nevertheless, making participants reflect on their carbon footprint was necessary to ensure that between-group differences in moral self- were only due to information provision about emissions reduction and not because the high awareness group's attention was more focused on low-carbon behaviour. Besides, the manipulation aimed at providing the license to generate a negative spillover was probably less effective than in common behavioural spillover studies because, in this

case, the first behaviour (i.e. halting normal life due to COVID-19) was not an individual but a collective behaviour in which individuals did not voluntarily decide to participate. Such an abstract construal of the initial behaviour tends to hinder its licensing potential (Mullen and Monin 2016). In addition, framing the behaviour that led to emissions reduction as an action that was not optional may have robbed some of its licensing potential because the moral evaluation of compulsory actions and voluntary actions is different (Vincent and Koessler 2020). Following Vincent and Koessler (2020), behavioural spillover research could benefit from more studies focused on the moral categories (i.e. optional, obligatory and forbidden) of the actions that lead to moral licensing.

Moreover, the relationship between environmental intentions and future actions may not be as direct as expected (Kormos, Gifford, and Brown 2015) because participants may have overstated their intentions to act pro-environmentally due to self-presentation effects and social-desirability bias. In their meta-analytic study, Maki et al. (2019) show that behavioural spillover studies in the environmental domain obtained stronger results when measuring intentions rather than actual behaviour. Future research should address the proposed relationships with a longitudinal design to confirm the translation of intention to behaviour.

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Table 1. Variables and measurement items

Variables	Items and scales	Reference	Mean	Std. Dev.	Cronbach's α
Moral self-concept (4 items)	<p><i>5-point semantic differential scale</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>In the wrong / in the right</i> • <i>Unethical / ethical</i> • <i>Guilty / virtuous</i> • <i>Ashamed / proud</i> 	Khan and Dhar (2006)	2.98	.88	.913
Environmental self-identity (3 items)	<p><i>5-point Likert scale (strongly disagree – strongly agree)</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Acting pro-environmentally is an important part of who I am.</i> • <i>I am the type of person who acts in an environmentally friendly way.</i> • <i>I see myself as an environmentally friendly person.</i> 	Van der Werff, Steg, and Keizer (2013)	3.62	.92	.881
Low-carbon behaviour (7 items)	<p><i>5-point Likert scale (very unlikely – very likely)</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Save electricity at home.</i> • <i>Avoid driving a car by using public transport or a bicycle or walking.</i> • <i>Offset my carbon emissions (for example, by paying for tree-planting).</i> • <i>Avoid buying new goods by using the ones I have.</i> • <i>Substitute meat with vegan products.</i> • <i>Sign up for a green electricity contract.</i> • <i>Turn down the heating or air conditioning at home.</i> 	Adapted from Kaiser and Wilson (2004)	3.08	.79	.744
Climate-harmful behaviour (7 items)	<p><i>5-point Likert scale (very unlikely – very likely)</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Use disposable (single use) paper or plastic products.</i> • <i>Drive instead of using public transport or walking.</i> • <i>Buy new goods instead of using the ones I have (clothes, appliances, furniture, car, etc.).</i> • <i>Prioritise price over environmental attributes when shopping.</i> • <i>Avoid taking flights [reverse-coded].</i> • <i>Use more electricity at home.</i> • <i>Turn up the heating or air conditioning at home.</i> 	Adapted from Bissing-Olson, Fielding, and Iyer (2016)	2.89	.74	.704
Behavioural cost of adapting to COVID-19 actions (4 items)	<p><i>5-point Likert scale (very much – not at all / Very severe – not severe at all)</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>To what degree were you affected by a lockdown or similar stay-at-home measure due to the COVID-19 outbreak?</i> • <i>How severe was the lockdown that affected you?</i> • <i>How have you experienced the measures to reduce the spread of the COVID-19?</i> • <i>How much effort did you have to make to adapt to stay-at-home measures, social distancing, and changes to everyday life derived from the COVID-19 outbreak?</i> 	Adapted from Carrico et al. (2018)	3.54	.98	.839

Table 2. Mean values of moral self-concept, low-carbon behaviour and climate-harmful behaviour, by emissions reduction awareness and norm manipulation.

Variables	Norm's manipulation	Emissions reduction awareness		Mean difference	t
		Low	High		
Moral self-concept	Control	2.86 (0.83)	3.31 (0.84)	-0.45	-4.33***
	Active	2.88 (0.98)	2.87 (0.80)	0.01	0.12
Low-carbon behaviour	Control	3.13 (0.79)	2.98 (0.74)	0.15	1.55
	Active	3.07 (0.80)	3.16 (0.84)	-0.08	-0.78
Climate-harmful behaviour	Control	2.89 (0.67)	2.90 (0.67)	-0.01	-0.10
	Active	2.82 (0.68)	2.77 (0.74)	0.05	0.57

Note. * $p < .05$; ** $p < .01$; *** $p < .001$. Standard deviations are reported in parenthesis next to the mean values.

Table 3. Conditional effects on moral self-concept at different values of moderators norm activation and environmental self-identity

Env. Norms	Environmental self-identity	Conditional effect	SE	t	LLCI (95%)	ULCI (95%)
0 (Control)	2.70 (-1SD)	.59	.13	4.55***	.3336	.8409
0 (Control)	3.62 (M)	.43	.11	4.00***	.2203	.6471
0 (Control)	4.54 (+1SD)	.28	.14	2.03*	.0095	.5508
1 (Active)	2.70 (-1SD)	.16	.14	1.14	-.1147	.4311
1 (Active)	3.62 (M)	.01	.11	.04	-.2112	.2205
1 (Active)	4.54 (+1SD)	-.15	.13	-1.15	-.4043	.1064

Note. * $p < .05$; ** $p < .01$; *** $p < .001$.

Table 4. Moderated mediation analysis and conditional indirect effects of emission reduction awareness at different values of the moderators

Variables	Moderator		Mod. med. index	Boot SE	Boot LLCI	Boot ULCI
Low-carbon behaviour	Env. norms activation		.11	.04	.03	.20
	Env. self-identity		.05	.02	.01	.09
Climate-harmful behaviour	Env. norms activation		-.05	.03	-.11	-.01
	Env. self-identity		-.02	.01	-.05	-.01
Variables	Values M (norms)	Values M (env. self-identity)	Cond. ind. effect	Boot SE	Boot LLCI	Boot ULCI
Low-carbon behaviour	0 (Control)	2.70 (-1SD)	-.14	.04	-.21	-.07
	0 (Control)	3.62 (M)	-.10	.03	-.17	-.05
	0 (Control)	4.54 (+1SD)	-.07	.04	-.14	-.01
	1 (Active)	2.70 (-1SD)	-.04	.03	-.10	.03
	1 (Active)	3.62 (M)	.001	.03	-.05	.05
	1 (Active)	4.54 (+1SD)	.03	.03	-.03	.10
Climate-harmful behaviour	0 (Control)	2.70 (-1SD)	.06	.03	.01	.12
	0 (Control)	3.62 (M)	.05	.02	.01	.10
	0 (Control)	4.54 (+1SD)	.03	.02	-.001	.08
	1 (Active)	2.70 (-1SD)	.02	.02	-.01	.05
	1 (Active)	3.62 (M)	.001	.01	-.03	.03
	1 (Active)	4.54 (+1SD)	-.02	.02	-.06	.01

Note. 10,000 bootstrap samples for 95% bootstrap confidence intervals.

Figure 1. Theoretical model

Figure 2. Effects of awareness of COVID-19-induced emissions reduction and normative influence on moral self-concept

Note. Error bars represent 95% confidence intervals.

Figure 3. Effects of the awareness of COVID-19-induced emissions reduction and environmental self-identity on moral self-concept

Note. High environmental self-identity (+1SD) = 4.54; environmental self-identity mean (M) = 3.62; low environmental self-identity (-1SD) = 2.70. Error bars represent 95% confidence intervals.